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Conduct photonics for investment in France and Slovakia

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1. Introduction

The second workpackage (WP2) of Photonics4All project “Outreach for promoting photonics to entrepreneurs” aims to promote photonics to both future and established entrepreneurs, and also give photonics entrepreneurs support in the development of their activities.

Many tools and activities have been developed during the project for entrepreneurs: brochures "Study photonics" where information is given where to learn various Photonics fields in different EU countries; “Create your business in photonics!” brochure focused on photonics technologies and related sectors with a regional focus on the need of these industries; organisation of photonics Boot Camps; Open Innovation workshops and methodology; startup challenges.

Task 2.5 “Photonics for investments” focuses on the support and investment in innovative ideas and photonics applications. The objective of the task is to provide the opportunity for Photonics SMEs to present their products or services during pitch presentations to new customers and investors. The aims of Task 2.5 coherently interplay with the other business-related activities of Photonics4all, such as aforementioned Photonics BootCamps or Innovation Workshops. Main focus of investment events is targeted at already established companies, looking for money to develop their products & services. This activity can be relevant either for newly established SMEs / startups or the older ones - depending on their development stage and the type of product. It also supports establishment of sustainable ecosystem of academic and industrial institutions, such as Photonics Clusters where new ideas emerging in research and development can be transferred to industry by direct contact between the partners.

In general, WP 2 covers all the life cycle of a photonics company’s needs: a young person starts studying photonics, then participates to events on entrepreneurship, then creates its company in a specific market, then tries to find new ideas and funding opportunities.

The Photonics for Investment events have three main objectives. The first objective is to connect entrepreneurs looking for funds with private investors seeking to invest their money. The second objective is to inform and educate private investors, not only on commercial and financial opportunities related to photonic technologies, but also about their specificities (degree of disruptiveness, R&D maturation, generic technologies, capital intensive, low scalability etc.). The third objective is to enable entrepreneurs to gain experience on the art of the pitch, which is becoming more and more usefull for them.

The expected impacts of these events were the following:

- high number of investors participating
- relevant number of matching between entrepreneurs and investors

- a further more qualitative matching between participants after the events (study of the project, appointment for a thorough discussion and finally a fundraiser).

Two partners of the project were involved in this task: ILC and Opticsvalley:

- International Laser Centre (Slovakia): ILC is the key national platform for education, research and development in the field of lasers and photonics in Slovakia. It is an interdisciplinary research organization with 23 employees, aimed to foster collaborative research between scientists and engineers by creating alliances and project teams among Slovak universities, academic institutions and industry. The Centre was created by the Ministry of Education of the Slovak Republic in January 1997 as an independent research and educational institution. Since its establishment ILC collaborates very closely with diverse local companies related to various Photonics branches, such as optical communication, microscopy, welding and material processing, up to education or showbusiness. ILC is also a member of the Laserlab Europe, where - in addition to collaborative research - it co-ordinates the user-training activities and plays a role of National contact-point in Slovakia. It has also representatives in European Technological Platform Photonics 21 and is a member of ECOP and EPIC (European Photonics Industry Consortium). ILC regularly organizes mid-size international meetings and workshops, such as LALS'98, LPHYS'02, ECONOS 2006, etc.

When describing the activities held in Slovakia it is noteworthy to say that Photonics and science in general is still underdeveloped in Slovakia in 2016. Thus, this case serves a model of the country where Photonics is mostly an unknown word in both scientific and business environments. This constitutes a serious restriction, but also strong motivation to find ways of introducing new products, startups and companies in this field.

- Opticsvalley (France): OV is the Paris-Region's network in the fields of Optics, Electronics and Software. Today **Opticsvalley**, with a staff of 17 employees, develops support actions for its over 200 members: SMEs, large corporations and research labs.

Through its network animation, information dissemination (over 12000 contacts in enterprises, labs, academic institutions, etc.) and support activities, **Opticsvalley** promotes innovation, contributes to the Paris-Region's economic development, by fostering the region's attractiveness and activity, supports the development of other regional & local actors and facilitates the convergence of optics, electronics and software engineering. Specific support to SMEs has been developed by **Opticsvalley** which provides individual support to SMEs and their development projects: a tailor-made service and methodology offering analysis, concerted evaluations and action plans, focused on the SME's development project, including the mobilization of different resources (R&D partners, financing, training, export, business operation...). Furthermore

Opticsvalley has been partner or coordinator of European projects since many years, and is member of Photonics21 and EPIC.

OV has close links with other national and European photonics clusters, and in the Paris region with local authority representatives and stakeholders for the economic development of SMEs (investors, networks, French Tech, associations, business clubs...).

Thanks to their expertise and available links to business networks the ILC and OV were relevant representatives of the framework able to organize Photonics for Investments events.

2. Overview of event and schedule

Within Task 2.5 four investment events have been delivered in total within the period of 2015-2016:

Event name	Date	Location	Main tools	Number of total participants / SMEs	Highlight
Day of Photonics	21.10.2015	Bratislava	TEDx talks	90 / 9 companies	Participation of 6 EU projects and state representatives
Photonics Venture Summit	13.06.2016	Paris	Working groups to prepare SMEs to the event Pitches during the event Feedback / evaluation to SMEs by investors Survey after the event	174 / 75	Methodology to support SMEs before and after the event. 1st results: 9 private meetings planned between SMEs and investors
INPHO Venture Summit	6-7.10.2016	Bordeaux	Round tables on photonics market trends Pitches (after coaching) 1/1 meetings with investors	130 / 60	Assessment of pitches by investors before the event Participation of big investors and large groups 5.000 € award for the winning pitching startup
Day of Photonics	21.10.2016	Bratislava	pitch presentations, round table	24 / 7 companies	Strengthening the Slovak Photonics Cluster network

3. Photonics Venture summit – 13th June 2016 – Paris, France

A. Description of the activity

Opticsvalley organized a [Photonics Venture Summit](http://www.opticsvalley.org/Les-Actualites/Agenda/Prix-Fibre-de-l-innovation-Opticsvalley/(event_id)/54336) ([http://www.opticsvalley.org/Les-Actualites/Agenda/Prix-Fibre-de-l-innovation-Opticsvalley/\(event_id\)/54336](http://www.opticsvalley.org/Les-Actualites/Agenda/Prix-Fibre-de-l-innovation-Opticsvalley/(event_id)/54336)) on the 13th June 2016 in Paris, at the „Paris Diderot“ University.

This event was part of a larger event we organized: “[Journée Opticsvalley - Le photon, moteur de l'innovation](http://www.opticsvalley.org/Les-Actualites/Agenda/Journee-Opticsvalley-Le-photon-moteur-de-l-innovation/(event_id)/53931)” ([http://www.opticsvalley.org/Les-Actualites/Agenda/Journee-Opticsvalley-Le-photon-moteur-de-l-innovation/\(event_id\)/53931](http://www.opticsvalley.org/Les-Actualites/Agenda/Journee-Opticsvalley-Le-photon-moteur-de-l-innovation/(event_id)/53931)).

This event gathered 174 participants, under the general topic of „Photon, the key to Innovation“. Four applicative sectors for photonics were highlighted: health, smart sustainable living, smart manufacturing, and play & learn.

Among the 174 participants, 75 of them were SMEs (including 25 startups).

The charts below provide details on type of participants.

The venture summit, based on fund raising, was organized in the framework of the International „[Creative Business Cup](http://www.creativebusinesscup.com)“ contest (<http://www.creativebusinesscup.com>). The objective was to select the French participant for the Global Finals which will take place in Copenhagen Business School end of November 2016.

The event had three main objectives. The first objective was to connect entrepreneurs looking for funds with private investors seeking to invest their money. The second objective was to inform and educate private investors, not only on commercial and financial opportunities related to photonic technologies, but also about their specificities (degree of disruptiveness, R&D maturation, generic technologies, capital intensive, low scalability...). The third objective was to enable entrepreneurs to gain experience on the art of the pitch, which is becoming more and more useful for them as more and more “pitches” are used to convince investors. Sometimes, companies also have to pitch to ask for public grants. For crowdfunding, things have changes also: before companies used to give information on their activities in a written way or videos on the websites of crowdfunding players, but today it often happens during „physical“ events where they have to pitch (eg: events „Kiss Kiss Bank Bank“, „So we fund“ in Paris...).

During this event, 13 startups pitched in front of 29 investors from different categories: venture capital, business angels, corporate investment, crowd-funding etc.

In parallel, 2 experts in finance gave a feedback to the photonics community attending. The 2 experts were the following:

- RAIZERS - Alexandre BERNARDI, Business developer
- FINANCIEL CONSEIL, Pascal DECOMBIS, CEO

The main feedback from the investors is that startups need to be well prepared (coached) before pitching.

The photonics SMEs were able during this event to identify financing opportunities, network, exhibit their products & services, and – as already mentioned - for 13 of them to pitch.

Regarding the exhibition aspects, this was done during the pitches: some companies showed their products to the audience. During the networking session that followed the pitches, startups were also able to present their products & services, but there were no specific booths available.

The list of participating startups and investors can be found in annexes 1 and 2.

B. Methodology

Beyond the traditional aspects of agenda and content (speakers, budget, location), Opticsvalley tried to be vigilant to create a good match between startups and investors in view of the wide variety of private investing (crowdfunding, bank, business angels, venture capital, corporate capital, family office etc.), to ensure the relevance of the event (i.e. the effectiveness of matchmaking). The matchmaking was organized around the pitches & networking sessions (no pre-planned 1/1 meetings).

The startup candidates had to fill in an application form to be selected for the pitches.

The requested information was the following:

- Contact details
- Economic and financial data: sector of activity, turnover, number of employees, patent
- Expenses: in R&D, personal costs, functioning, marketing, manufacturing
- Description of product & technology
- Applicative markets
- Business model
- Previous experience in funding: which level, amount?
- Details on funding request: objective, amount, type of investor?

It was indeed important to ensure a good fit between startups and investors considering the following points in particular:

- the amount of desired funds raised;
- the maturity of the startup (pre-creation, creation, post creation VS capital development);
- the industry the startup belongs to.

In terms of content, beyond the startup pitch (3-7 minutes), it has been very useful that investors expressed their needs and their investment strategies to educate entrepreneurs and to make them – eventually – change their business plan.

The fact that startups and investors were gathered in the same place allowed them to exchange on their strategies (investors) and needs & specificities (startups).

To organize the event, we first set-up some working groups with startups and SME, in march to define their expectation and the difficulties encountered in raising funds and talking with financial partners. This revealed two points:

- first that ventures were scared often by the word „photonics“ and that it had no added value today within the financial community
- second that photonics SME had some specificities in their business model and scale-up organization that required to find some appropriate more patient funds.

Therefore, we have launched since then, a sensibilization campaign to bring more value to the term „photonics“, to make it a hot spot for ventures.

C. Impact measurement & follow-up

Opticsvalley set up 2 ways to evaluate the impact of the event on the photonics SME's:

1/ Evaluation during the event

First of all, the SMEs which pitched have been evaluated by investors during their speech and given a score with comments. This evaluation was based on 3 criteria:

- market (business model, market potential),
- technology (technological maturity and potential)
- verbal skills (the way the company speaks and presents itself).

We think that giving this feedback from investors to the pitching SMEs can definitely help them for further fundraising activities.

The template used for the evaluation is in annex 3.

2/ Survey

A few weeks after the event, Opticsvalley sent participating SMEs a survey asking them how many contacts they had during the event with investors, if they had depth conversations with them, if their request has been studied, if they had appointment with investors, if they managed to get financing, and if yes how much?

See Template for qualitative impact measurement in annex 4.

The results of the survey are the following:

- 34 contacts between photonics SMEs and investors were made during the event
- out of which 14 business have been examined
- and out of which 9 SMEs were invited to a private meeting with investors

D. Conclusion

This event was beneficial for entrepreneurs because, apart from enabling them to raise funds, it allowed them to better understand the expectations and strategies (including exit strategies) of investors who are part of a very varied population.

This type of event is also useful to the European photonics industry as it increases awareness of investors to the characteristics of photonic companies. They witness « entrepreneurial effervescence » and business opportunities of photonics startups, which may result in the opening of specific funds more suitable for photonics companies.

Finally, this type of event is positive for photonics clusters as Opticsvalley because it improves the quality of their support in future funds raising actions, in particular by optimizing the match-making based on many criteria, such as maturity of project, nature of projects, type of business model (BtoB or BtoC,...).

Annex 5: Teaser of the event

4. INPHO Venture Summit – 6 & 7 October 2016 – Bordeaux, France

A Description of the activity

Opticsvalley was partner in the organization of the [INPHO Venture Summit](#), the event for executives active in smart technologies including photonics and smart businesses in Bordeaux.

This event gathers every 2 years large companies, venture capitalists and startups to meet to develop collaborations while exchanging on key bankable challenges to invest in.

Type of participants	Number of participants
SMEs	31
Startups	29
Investors	40
Large companies	20
Institutional	10
Total	130

Number of round tables	7
Number of Elevator pitches	4
Number of pitching startups	19

This year, the program focused on 4 main applicative sectors for photonics: Energy Efficiency, Health/consumer, Telecom/datacom and Mobility/autonomous vehicle.

For each of these topics a round-table was organized to discuss market trends and needs, and photonics companies were given the opportunity to pitch in front of investors.

In parallel to the round tables, the SMEs could also meet the investors during one to one meeting set-up for them in an open innovation framework by a dedicated consultant. These 1/1 meetings were for most of them planned in advance, but a lot also happened “in situ”, during the networking sessions & breaks. The investors were easily identifiable by SMEs as they were either speakers or moderators during the round tables.

Leading European and Silicon Valley C-level executives like Facebook, Ciena, First Solar, Free, Schneider Electric, Legrand, Johnson&Johnson, PSA Peugeot Citroën, Bosch, EDF Energies Nouvelles etc. joined the Summit.

Annex 6: Teaser of the event.

Annex 7: Program of the event.

B. Methodology

Regarding the **round-tables**, the choice of topics was discussed early 2016 by the organisational committee of the event, including SMEs and technological experts. The final choice of the 4 topics mentioned above is the result of these discussions and bibliographic searches.

For each round table, there was a speech by one sponsor and an introduction by a large company or a relevant stakeholder on the selected market (market trend, needs in terms of photonics innovation...). The draft for each round table was then submitted to the moderator, ahead of the event.

To ensure a high-quality **elevator-pitch**, all submissions were assessed ahead of time by a Selection Committee made up of technical experts and investors.

Opticsvalley was part of this selection committee, under the framework of the Photonics4All project.

To be mentioned that all participants paid a 450€ fee to attend the meeting, so this was already a first selection to ensure that participating companies were really involved and mature for fund raising (they didn't just come to listen).

In total, 20 selected startups have been coached by experts and financial advisors to be ready for their 5 minutes presentation. Each presentation was then followed by a 2 minutes questions/answers session.

The list of the pitching companies is in annex 8.

In the end, 5.000€ cash was awarded to the most promising company.

C. Impact measurement & follow-up

The winner of the INPHO 2016 elevator pitches was Chronocam (www.chronocam.com). Chronocam is developing a unique, bio-inspired and self-adapting approach to the need for visual sensing and processing in autonomous vehicles, connected devices, security and surveillance systems.

In addition to the pitch award, Chronocam raised 15 million € thanks to the contacts established during the summit.

Regarding the impact and outcomes for the other companies, the event is too recent to be able to provide feedback yet. A follow-up survey will be sent in February 2017.

5. Day of Photonics, 21.10.2015 and 2016, Bratislava Slovakia

A. Description of the activity

On the 21st October we are remembering the anniversary of an event, when - in 1983 - the General Conference on Weights and Measures adopted value of 299,792.458 km/s as the constant speed of light. The "Day of Photonics" format was developed and promoted by EPIC consortium ([www. http://day-of-photonics.org](http://day-of-photonics.org)) and is intended to link the academic and the industrial worlds. In Slovakia, this day has been celebrated since 2014 with the aim to reunite top science, research, technology, innovation and industry in the field of Photonics, as well as to encourage entrepreneurs to look towards photonics when thinking about creating new companies, products or solutions.

During the International Year of Light and Light-based Technologies (YIL) 2015, three European projects GoPhoton!, LIGHT2015 and Photonics4all aimed together to convince entrepreneurs in Europe to see photonics as a technological area with large market potential, area where big things happen and with high social impact. This was the foundation of our decision to organize Day of Photonics 2015 as a highlight of the YIL in Slovakia with the presence and support of all these projects together.

B. Methodology

All sessions of the Day of Photonics in 2015 were presented in the form of "LIGHTTalks", which is the alternative of TEDx (<https://www.ted.com/about/programs-initiatives/tedx-program>) – presentations followed by panel discussion developed by Institute of Photonics Sciences (ICFO), Barcelona. ILC has adopted this format from ICFO as a recent member of ECOP alliance (<http://ecopalliance.eu>).

LIGHTtalks consist of an array of live presenters from the scientific, entrepreneurial and industry communities speaking about different aspects of photonics. The specific feature of the LIGHTtalks series is that through the profiles that are made available, talks are delivered using a predefined format and with guidelines and advice provided to local organizers to simplify the setting up and implementation of the events.

While the profiles predefine the structure and topic of the LIGHTtalks, organizers are responsible for:

- Identifying the venue and the speakers
- Promote and disseminate the activity
- Implement the activity

The template profiles developed for the event (Annex 9) set the framework of the activity and ensure easy replication, at the same time that allows an adaptation of the activity to the local idiosyncrasy, allowing the organizer to take into consideration the local research and industry landscape into consideration when identifying the speakers.

The final goal was to increase the interest of industry in photonics, encourage established business people to use photonics technologies and create open channels of communications with established business people currently outside of the photonics arena.

Upon special recommendation of Light2015, business dinner was added to the Day of Photonics event as a space for informal discussions between the industrial and academic partners after the formal program.

C. Day of Photonics 2015

This event was the climax of activities of the International Year of Light 2015 in Slovakia and major event for Photonics outreach in Slovakia in 2015. Joined effort of GoPhoton!, Photonics4all and Light2015 projects, EPIC initiative and ILC SPIE Student chapter provided a possibility to students and young scientists for direct experience sharing with senior scientists, entrepreneurs and industry.

The Day of Photonics began with the seminar “Photonics for future”, on perspectives of the use of photonics technologies in the present time and in the future. In the next morning session, “Photonics for careers”, perspective young researchers and students learned about possibilities of career opportunities in the field of Photonics. Both these modules were integral part of GoPhoton! Splash event. In the framework of the special SPIE lecture, Prof. Pavel Cheben talked on “Latest advances in integrated silicon photonics”. In the afternoon, the event continued with a thematic session “Photonics for investment”, focusing on the discussion and exchange of information about possibilities of support and investment in new applications, products and innovative ideas in Photonics. In the last part of the event, entitled “The Power of Photonics”, company presentations were followed by discussion on multidisciplinary applications and use of Photonics in practice such as healthcare or industry. These last two modules were delivered in collaboration of the projects Photonics4all (Photonics4investment) and Light2015 (Power of Photonics).

Day of Photonics 2015 was organized by ILC under the auspices of the Minister of education, science, research, and sport of the Slovak Republic, supported by 3 EU/H2020 grants designed for popularisation of the International Year of Light 2015. Last but not least, the bilateral discussion between the secretary of state of the Ministry and representative of ELI DC¹ was held during the meeting, with the theme of possible closer collaboration of Slovakia within ELI project. Detailed program of this event is included in Annex 10.

Statistics:

- *Attendees: 90*, mainly from Slovakia but also from Czech Republic, Poland, Belgium, Canada.
- *Gender statistics: 19 females, 71 males.*
- *Number of academic institutions: 5* (ILC; FEI STU; University of Zilina; Institute of Electrotechnics Slovak academy of sciences; Institute of Astronomy, Slovak academy of sciences)
- *Number of representatives of Ministry: 3* (Kanovska, Putalova, Hermanovska)
- *Number of representatives of professional photonics societies: 5* representatives of 3 societies (Czechoslovak microscopy society, Czech and Slovak society for Photonics, SPIE)
- *Representatives of EU projects (in addition to GoPhoton!, P4all and Light2015): 3* (Eurobioimaging, ELI, Acfast)
- *Number of industrial participants: 9* companies, out of which 7 SME's (PowerTec, Sylex, LEDeco solution, Kvant, NMS, Avantek, Prva Zvaracska).

D. Day of Photonics 2016

In 2016 we celebrated 21st of October as a Day of Photonics for the third time. In contrast to the previous year we decided to split the popularization part dedicated to general public and academic audience, which was organized on October 20 in the city of Zilina to reach even more attendees and future photonics students from broader region of central Slovakia, and to ILC Open Day which was organized in the morning of 21st October at ILC with the support of Photonics4all.

The industry-oriented module, consisting in the meeting of Slovak Photonics Cluster in Bratislava and organized directly under the framework of Photonics4all project was held at the premises of Slovak Technical University in Bratislava. The general academic presentations were supported also by ILC SPIE Student chapter, which

¹ ELI = Extreme Light Infrastructure, ELI-DC= ELI-Delivery Consortium International Association, an international non-profit organisation coordinating the implementation phase of the ELI research infrastructure

provided a possibility to students and young scientists for direct experience sharing with senior scientists, entrepreneurs and industry representatives.

During the Day of Photonics 2016 in Bratislava, ILC presented the results of Photonics4all projects, including the prototype of OmniLight Laboratory and the concept of Festival of Light in Bratislava. In addition to already traditional contributions from Slovak Photonics Cluster members, we had a privilege to hear the lecture from Photoneo startup (<https://www.photoneo.com>), a winner of the Slovakia Startup awards 2015 in the category of Science with its innovative 3D sensor.

Presentations of companies working in the field of photonics were followed by intense discussion and business dinner, with the themes related the needs of the industrial sector towards academia, as well as defining of framework for education of Photonics, still not yet accredited as the official scientific discipline in Slovakia.

Statistics of industrial participants: 7 SME companies (MicroStep, Sylex, Avantek, Prva Zvaracska, Kvant, Photoneo, Carl Zeiss Slovakia)

Presentation of Photoneo at the Day of Photonics 2016.

E. Impact measurement

Organizers were asked to provide the number of different stakeholders contacted for the event, and how many of those were engaged (see statistics described in each particular event).

Satisfaction level of attendants was measured at different levels by personal interviews:

1. General level about the liking of the activity, structure, length, speakers: in this regard we received positive feedback, except for the overall length of the event on 21.10.2015 which was bit overwhelming for the attendants (9 hours). This was the reason why in 2016 we divided the Day of Photonics to two parts - one focused on general public and students, and second one on entrepreneurs, startups and industry/academy liaisons.
2. Attendants were asked if the LIGHTtalk had been helpful in better understanding their current or future business, the feedback was positive

towards focused 10min. presentations of clearly defined business ideas followed by discussion, rather than lengthy descriptions.

3. Important feedback was related to the opinion of industry participants on which activities provided by academic institutions are /would be helpful for their business. It seems that the most important areas where academy can provide assistance to industry is human resource development, trainings and joined short projects/experiments for addressing and solving actual technological challenges.

F. Conclusion & follow-up

The most important outcome of the two years of Photonics4all support in the area of Investment in Photonics is sustainable operation of **Slovak Photonics Cluster** network. While still in an informal state, we developed good interconnection with leading Slovak SME's in the field of Photonics with great interest expressed for continuation of such collaboration in the future years.

The undisputed leader of Industrial venture activities in Slovakia is Neology corp. (www.neology.com), the organizer of annual Startup awards in Slovakia (<http://www.startupawards.sk>). In 2015 we had discussed the possibility of collaboration related to the Day of Photonics, but unfortunately with no direct outcome. On the other hand, we initiated evaluation of several innovative ideas in photonics which has been provided by Neology experts in 2015. We are also in contact with large-scale corporations such as Samsung Display Slovakia, trying to invite them to join Slovak Photonics cluster. To summarize our experience, interconnection of research, development and business in Photonics is apparently still under threshold for recognizing its importance and individual character in Slovakia, and more effort will be needed to gain positive results in the future development of this field.

6. Other initiatives in France: investor's club

In addition to the organization of Photonics Venture Summits, Opticsvalley started to think about the creation of an **Investor's club for Photonics**, based on experience gained during the project. This action will be launched in 2017, so after the Photonics4All project, but it is relevant to say a few words about it in this section as the preparation has already started in 2016.

The decision to overtake such a new activity was partially impulse by the lessons learnt from the investment events: it definitely comforted Opticsvalley in going further in this field. The objective is to gather investors representing all categories, that is to say venture capitalists, business angels, crowd-funding, corporate funding, etc. Today, 5 venture capitalists have already given us their approval, and the good thing is that they represent all the top applicative markets for photonics (robotics, laser...).

Opticsvalley will contribute to the deal-flow, meaning that thanks to the visits we do in photonics companies, we will be able to select the ones relevant for investors (investors don't usually have the time to identify such prospects). By putting together our efforts (investors & Opticsvalley) to identify startups, we cover a wider spectrum of startups looking for funding.

The objective is to organize up to 2 meetings per year, for investors to provide feedback on the applications we will present them. These investors will be able to join Opticsvalley's board of stakeholders, and thus give us advice on the actions we wish to implement regarding funding for photonics companies.

The final objective is to increase the awareness of different types of investors on the photonics sector.

7. Other initiatives in Slovakia: Festival of Light

Since 2015 when the first Festival of Light in Bratislava was organized as an integral part of PhotonicsSplash Bratislava (project GoPhoton!), we had adopted a vision that this kind of event can attract interest of both investors and decision makers to recognize the power of Photonics technologies and related industry and business. With this mission in mind, Festival was organized in 2016 as a completely independent event. Photonics4all project played a crucial role in the success of this newly established format by supporting its exhibits and organisation. Our goal was to create a sustainable format of a festival combining intelligent technologies, contemporary art and state-of-the-art solutions with added value, with the focus given on presentation and interconnection of companies related to photonics, young creative professionals and the modern city. The base of the event was installations using light as a medium to transfer perception, interaction or experience.

The organizer of this event was civic association SEA (Science and Education Agency) in cooperation with Bratislava - the Capital City of Slovak Republic and City District of Bratislava - Stare Mesto (Old Town). Aside from being artistic, the installations served also as a medium of **presentation of the innovative companies**. In particular, following photonics - and creative industry - related companies has been involved in the event: Kvant, LEDeco, Q99, LaserMedia, Akasha Visualstation, SiProgs, Ogmium; together with other established large business partners, such as Slovak Telecom, Philips or Eurovea shopping mall. The important lesson we learned from organizing this event was that indeed this might be a suitable format for **attracting interest of potential investors**, coherently to the public display of new innovative technologies developed by state-of-the-art companies.

8. Lessons learnt and recommendations

What are the main **lessons learned** from these venture forums organized for Photonics SMEs?

The feedback from investors is mostly the same from one event to the other, this is why it has been summarized in this conclusion. The main outcomes are:

- SMEs, and especially startups, really do need to be coached ahead of the events
- Photonics SMEs should NOT focus their speeches on technological aspects (it is not relevant for investors and they sometimes don't understand such technical degree of precision)
- SMEs should rather emphasize their speeches on the amount they are looking for fund raise, and on their objectives (why do they need the money?)
- SMEs should develop on the added value of their products/services (and not on how it works)

So the main advice to SMEs pitching is: "Talk less about technology and more about the use on the market!"

It is indeed specific and more challenging to raise funds for SMEs such as the Photonics ones working on "hard" technologies versus software ones. For photonics companies, more fund for investment is needed to scale-up.

In addition to the abovementioned experience, we realized that important areas where academy can provide assistance to the already established companies is human resource development, trainings and joined short projects/experiments for addressing and solving actual technological challenges.

What are the main **Policy recommendations**?

To strengthen and ensure future investments in the photonics industry, policy makers should :

- Contribute to the creation of an investment funds which should be more adapted to the fundamentals of photonics startups, including taking (public) stakes in the funds, as does the BPI France in France. In this case, we need to extend efforts;
- Extend (local or national) tax policies and tax strategies to strengthen private investment in technological SMEs and startups (e.g. in France business angels can lower their tax contribution by investing in startups);
- Contribute to the implementation of a European venture summit to promote European private financing in promising photonic startups, based for example on the INPhO summit in Bordeaux (France)

9. Summary and conclusions

This task was very successful, as 4 Photonics4investment events in total were organized by the two contributors: Opticsvalley in France and International Laser Center in Slovakia. Other types of activities are reported as well, even if not mandatory in the project, but relevant to the theme: future creation of a Club of investors for Photonics in France, and sustainable development of the Slovak Photonics Cluster network.

Opticsvalley's venture summit will be organized once a year as of next year, as it has been very successful.

Regarding the Investor's club for Photonics, one objective is to provide investors with anonymous business plans from startups to evaluate their quality and give feedbacks to improve their chance to raise funds. This will be organised once a year beginning in 2017.

So in conclusion, we can summarize that:

- Opticsvalley disseminated funding demands in 2015, started organising venture summits in 2016, and will launch a new dynamic in 2017 with the creation of a specific investment fund for Photonics.
- ILC had organized two events bringing together Industrial and Academy environments and successfully established the Day of Photonics as a suitable format and gathering point of the Slovak Photonics Cluster network.

Annex 1: List of participants to Opticsvalley's Photonics Venture Summit – pitching startups

Name of company (with web link)	Representative of the company
DAMAE Medical	Anais BARUT
MIRSENSE	Mathieu CARRAS
NAPA TECHNOLOGIES	Daniel TUROVER
KEEN EYE TECHNOLOGIES	Sylvain BERLEMONT
CHECKUP SOLAR	Luc MEHRET
LIGHTON	Laurent DAUDET
CASCADE LIGHT TECHNOLOGIES	Frédéric PEILLERON
GREENTROPISM	Anthony BOULANGER
KUANTOM	Simon FALK
ENOVAP	Alexandre SCHECK
AQUATIX	Alain DINIS
CYCLOPUS	Jérémie ABOU
DREAMUP VISION	Ekaterina BESSE

Annex 2: List of participants to Opticsvalley's Photonics Venture Summit - investors

NAME	SURNAME	COMPANY	TYPE
ALLILAIRE	Etienne	ALTEREQUITY	VC
BAUDIER	Jacques	INSEAD BA	BA
BEN OSMAN	Salah	RAIZERS	Crowdfunder
BERNARDI	Alexandre	RAIZERS	Crowdfunder
COLLANGETTES	Fabien	PARIS BUSINESS ANGELS	BA
CORDELLE	Pierre	ASTER CAPITAL	VC
DÉPORTE	Maxime	IDINVEST	VC

DESPLAT	Jean-François	BUSINESS ANGELS DES GRANDES ECOLES	BA
DUVAL	Bruno	FINANCE ET TECHNOLOGIE	BA
FABRE	Jacques	INVESTESSOR	BA
FAVIER	Cédric	SEVENTURE PARTNERS	VC
GEFFROY	Philippe	LINKWEST GROUP	BA
GOBE	Alexis	SOCIÉTÉ GÉNÉRALE	Bank
IDRISSI	Karim	SOCIÉTÉ GÉNÉRALE	Bank
LE BOUDEC	Michel	SOCIÉTÉ GÉNÉRALE	Bank
LESAFFRE	Max	QUADRIVIUM VENTURES	VC
MAISTRE	Franck	BNP PARIBAS	Bank
METOIS	Ladislá	PLEIADES VENTURE	VC
MIROIS	Laurent	PLEIADES VENTURE	VC
MORDANT	Maurice	INVESTESSOR	BA
RICOEUR-NICOLAÏ	Nathalie	SCIENTIPÔLE CAPITAL	VC
THOMAS	Gabrielle	XANGE - SIPAREX PROXIMITÉ INNOVATION	VC
TOUTAIN MEUSNIER	Thomas	DURAPOLE	VC
TURKI	Wafa	SOCIÉTÉ GÉNÉRALE	Bank
SALHI	Mehdi	TOTAL DEVELOPPEMENT REGIONAL	Corporate venture
STASSINET	Aurélié	CMCIC Innovation	Bank
LEGAY	Jean-François	JFLC Innovations	BA
BALDOUN		CAP DECISIF	VC
MAUGE	Dimitri	SCIENTIPÔLE CAPITAL	VC

Annex 4: Template for qualitative impact measurement (Opticsvalley's Photonics Venture Summit)

Name of the company	Main activity	Number of employees	Country / region	Amount requested for funding	What the companies is asking money for?	Event / support action provided by P4All

Date of the event / action	Number of contacts with investors	In depth conversations with investors	Study of the request by investors	Appointment with investors	Financing OK ?	Amount of financing

Annex 5: Teaser Photonics Venture summit – 13th June 2016 – Paris

FUNDRAISING FOR PHOTONICS START-UPS

The Venture Summit aims to market the Photonics sector to a wider investor community (venture capital, business angels, corporate investment, crowdfunding...) and create channels to finance high potential photonics start-ups. As a start-up you get the change to present your business by applying for a pitching slot (optional).

4 TOPICS:

**HEALTH • SMART SUSTAINABLE LIVING • PLAY & LEARN
SMART MANUFACTURING**

OPTICSVALLEY'S VENTURE SUMMIT IS THE CHANCE FOR YOU TO:

- ◆ Identify financing opportunities
- ◆ Pitch to investors
- ◆ Network & meet French and other European photonics start-ups
- ◆ Exhibit your products & services on a booth dedicated to your company

> INFORMATION & REGISTRATION (BEFORE 27TH MAY) <

Please note that information on the web site is only provided in French, but if you are interested in participating/pitching, we will be more than happy to help you prepare your application and venue.

CONTACT : JONATHAN BAINEE | J.BAINEE@OPTICSVALLEY.ORG | +33 1 69 31 75 11

WHEN?

13 JUNE 2016
11:30 - 13:00

WHERE?

UNIVERSITY
PARIS DIDEROT CAMPUS (PARIS)

Event organised by

Partners and sponsors

Creative
Business
Cup

LEYTON

Annex 5: Teaser of INPHO Venture Summit – 6 & 7 October 2016 – Bordeaux

INPHO® is the event for executives active in smart technologies including photonics and smart businesses. It gathers large companies, VCs and start-ups to meet to develop collaborations while exchanging on key bankable challenges to invest in.

Meet with key European and Silicon Valley C-level executives

Leading European and Silicon Valley C-level executives like Facebook, Ciena, Juniper Network, First Solar, Free, Schneider Electric, Legrand, Johnson&Johnson, PSA Peugeot Citroën, Bosch, EDF Energies Nouvelles, and many more... are joining the INPHO® Venture Summit. They are looking for the game changers in energy efficiency, mobility/ autonomous vehicles, digital medicine and datacom/ telecom. They will be accessible for one-to-one meetings with participants in an open innovation framework organized by BLUMORPHO.

Pitch in front of international investors

INPHO® offers a unique opportunity to pitch in front of investors. All applicants will receive a concrete feedback on their growth strategy and investment readiness by private investors.

"I am pleased to chair a new chapter in the Bordeaux region's initiative to further private placement investment in disruptive hardware technologies. Each edition draws increasingly higher profile industrial players and investors with a singular objective: to strike a deal. INPHO® Venture Summit is an exciting place to be for high-level business networking in a unique setting where, over two days, everyone is accessible and very proactive."
Georges Ugras, Managing Director of IBM Venture Capital Group and Chair of the INPHO Venture Summit 2016

Participation process

If you are interested in [applying](#) for a pitch and the one-to-one meetings we need you to communicate this interest to us until **30 June 2016**. After applying for INPHO®, you will receive the feedback of the Selection Committee as well as the list of international companies you can book for one-to-one meetings.

For further information please visit www.inpho-ventures.com or contact [Ms Ramona Landgraf](#) (+33 145057046).

Annex 7: Program of the event (INPHO Venture Summit).

Event Schedule		
THURSDAY 6TH OF OCTOBER From 1:00pm to 11pm		
1:00pm Welcome Address	1:15pm IoT & Smartgrids: Toward new business models in Energy • Presentation of industrial needs and interests, "what keeps you up at night?" (no presentation, but concrete questions) • 5Elevator Pitches	2:45pm Disruptive Technologies Session
4:00pm What is the future of "mobility"?	5:30pm Boosting technology innovation through Equity Investments European Investment Fund	6:30pm Free time or "Exclusive Club" Networking
		7:00pm Gala Dinner Transportation to Chateau Pape-Clément
FRIDAY 7TH OF OCTOBER From 9:00am to 2pm		
9:00am Better data for better treatment	10:30am Coffee Break	12:15pm Europe attractiveness to innovate
	10:45am Telecom/Datacom: The cornerstone for the digital revolution	1:00pm Lunch for Networking & Award Ceremony

Annex 8: List of companies (startups) pitching at INPHO Venture Summit

Name of company	Country
BSQ Solar	Spain
XTPL	Poland
Cascade	France
BluemintLabs	France
ARYBALLE TECHNOLOGIES	France
Primo1D	France
Insightness	Switzerland
Drayson Technologies	UK
D-EYE	Italy
Argolight	France
DAMAE MEDICAL	France
VivoSensMedical	Germany
MedLumics	Spain
LunaLEC	Sweden
BeSpoon	France
itk	France
Chronocam	France
AEPONYX	Canada
EFFECT Photonics	Netherlands

Annex 9: TEDx LIGHTtalks: The Power of Photonics template by GoPhoton!

LIGHT2015
PHOTONICS
EUROPEAN PHOTONIC SOCIETY

ECOP
EUROPEAN
SOCIETY
FOR OUTREACH
IN PHOTONICS

<p>Description</p>	<p>A series of inspirational talks targeting industry focused on the multidisciplinary applications of photonics and their use in the industry.</p> <hr/> <p>Photonics research is rapidly flowing from research centres and laboratories to be incorporated into industrial processes. The session will be composed of a series of experienced speakers delivering talks that illustrate how a broad spectrum of photonic applications can be used and bring value add to different industries. There will be a special focus on cross-disciplinary, cross-KET, and cross-sector applications.</p> <p>The session will focus on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expose the potential of Photonics in industrial processes and innovation. • Emphasize the contribution of Photonics to the economy. • Highlight the ubiquity of Photonics. • Feature the increasingly central role of Photonics in areas such as Life Sciences, Quality Control, Agrofood and Cultural Patrimony.
<p>Objectives</p>	<p>This series strive to reach new sectors and industries where photonics may be applied to unleash innovative potential, improving industrial processes and brining new products to market. It aims to create awareness among industry members about the economic and industrial potential of photonics, thereby encouraging them to consider Photonics as an interesting field to integrate or to create new innovation areas in existing businesses.</p>
<p>Structure</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 5 min Introduction of the event and the speakers by the moderator. • 20 min Introduction about the power of photonics and its economic and technology impact. • 50 min (5x10min) Inspirational talks in pill format by each speaker (about 5 speakers). • 45 min Round table and Q&A session. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Distribute notes of paper that people can use to write their questions (and if possible names/company). - Have a set of questions ready in case nobody asks (or to trigger the questions). • 60-90 min Networking dinner. <p><u>Moderator:</u> node's representative.</p> <p><u>Key note speaker:</u> VIP profile (Partner's senior level representative): to provide the general context of the global photonics market.</p> <p><u>Potential Speakers:</u> Group of speakers that are developing / doing research in photonics technologies with industrial applications as well as industry members that can explain how they are using photonics technologies in their company. Different industry segments should be present, such as health, agro-food, photonics integrated circuits, energy, space and research markets, laser manufacturing, new materials, etc.</p> <p><u>Issues that could be addressed:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Global perspective of photonics. • How photonics is used to address various challenges in a particular industry. • Advantages of photonic technologies over the existing ones. • Economic impact of photonics.

Annex 10: Program of the Day of Photonics 2015 in Bratislava, Slovakia

Day of Photonics, October 21, 2015

- 8.30-8.35** **Welcome** – F.Uherek, director of International Laser Centre
- 8.35-8.45** **Introductory Remarks** of R. Kanovská, the secretary of state of the Ministry of Education, Science, Research and Sport of the Slovak Republic and M. Oravec, the Dean of the Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Information Technology of the Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava
- 8.45-10.00** **Block I. Photonics for Future (Project GoPhoton!)**
- 8.45-9.10** D. Pudiš, University of Žilina **Photonics in 21st century**
- 9.10-9.30** F. Uherek, ILC, **International year of light**
- 9.30-9.40** A. Putalová, CVTI SR, **Photonics and science outreach in Slovakia**
- 9.40-9.50** J. Kováč, FEI STU, **Institute of Photonics at Slovak University of Technology**
- 9.50-10.00** J. Novák, EIÚ SAV, **Photonics research at the Institute of Electrotechnics, Slovak Academy of Sciences**
- 10.00-10.10** V. Rušin, Institute of Astronomy, SAS, **Perspectives of photonics technologies in Astrophysics**
- 10.10-10.30** *Discussion and Coffee break*
- 10.30-11.40** **Block II. Photonics for careers (Project GoPhoton!)**
- 10.30-10.45** I. Hermanovská, National Contact Point of H2020, CVTI SR, **Careers and supporting programs in EU**
- 10.45-11.00** M. Donoval, **PowerTec, s.r.o.**
- 11.00-11.10** D. Chorvát, ILC, **Czechoslovak microscopy society and Eurobioimaging**
- 11.10-11.25** D. Senderáková, Czech and Slovak society for Photonics, **Photonics at schools - new efforts and approaches**
- 11.25-11.40** J.Horilová, A. Marček-Chorvátová, **ILC SPIE Student Chapter**
- 11.40 - 12.00** **Discussion**
- 12.00 - 13.00** *Lunch break*
- 13.00-14.00** **Special SPIE Student chapter lecture**
- 13.00-14.00** Pavel Cheben NRC Canada, Ottawa:
Photonics for future - exploiting subwavelength domain
- 14.00-15.20** **Block III. Photonics for investment (Project Photonics4All)**
- 14.00-14.20** Sylex, s.r.o.
- 14.20-14.35** LEDeco solution, s.r.o.
- 14.35-14.50** Kvant s.r.o.
- 14.50-15.05** NMS s.r.o.
- 15.05-15.20** Avantek s.r.o
- 15.20-15.50** *Discussion and Coffee break*
- 15.50-17.20** **Blok IV. The power of photonics (Project Light2015)**
- 15.50.-16.15** **The power of Photonics and its economic and technology impact**
- 16.05.-16.20** **ELI - the Extreme Light Infrastructure project**
- 16.20-16.35** M.Witkowski, **ACTPHAST**
- 16.35-16.50** I.Čavarga, **OÚSA Bratislava**
- 16.50-17.05** F.Kolenič a.s., **Laser and electron beam welding for automotive industry**
- 17.05-17.20** **Slovak lasero-therapeutic society: Lasers in medicine**
- 17.20-17.55** **Discussion**
- 17.55** **Closing ceremony**
- 18.00 - 19.30** *Business dinner (invited and registered guests)*